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Experimental Research Design: A Play of Variables

- Rajan Kumar Kandel
Teaching Assistant
English Language Education
Surkhet Campus (Education)

Abstract

Experimental research is a quantitative and empirical research carried out on the philosophical basis of positivism. It is based on experimentation and manipulation of the research variables during the study. A number of scientifically agreed steps are carried out from the formulation of research problems to writing the research report in experimental design. In this article, different experimental designs including pre-experimental designs, true experimental designs, and quasi-experimental designs are identified and illustrated comprehensively. This article provides a rationale for carrying out different kinds of experimental research designs in different social contexts. It discusses varied variables as the central manipulative and static devices in experiments. Finally, internal and external validity in experimental research design is described followed by potential threats to validity and some suggestions to avoid such threats jeopardizing validity of experimental research.

Key words: Experimental treatment, experimental and control group, placebo, research variables, research validity.

Introduction

Research design is the conceptual structure within which research is conducted. It consists of the blueprint for the collection, calculation and analysis of data. In this way, research design is an outline of the whole process of the study from hypothesis formulation to the final analysis of data. It specifies the sources and types of information, the approach used for gathering and analyzing the data, time and cost of the study, etc. Kothari (2009, pp. 31-32) mentions that the overall research design may be split into the sampling design, the observational design, the statistical design and the operational design. Thus, preparation of the research design should be done with great care because any error in it may spoil the entire project. We can classify the different research designs into three main categories viz. explanatory

research studies, descriptive and diagnostic research studies and hypothesis-testing research studies. Hypothesis-testing research designs are generally known as experimental research designs where the researcher tests the hypothesis of casual relationship between variables. According to Trochim (2006), experimental designs are often the most rigorous of all research designs. It is regarded as the 'gold standard' against which all other designs are judged. Experimental design, in fact, is a planned interference in the natural orders of a process by the researcher, not (only) the careful observation of what is occurring. The researcher actively interferes or manipulates the stream of events. A selected condition or a change (treatment) is introduced and observation or measurements are planned to illuminate the effect of any change in conditions.

The beginning of experimental design was made by Professor R. A. Fisher in agricultural research when he was working at Rothamsted Experimental Station, Centre for Agricultural Research in England (Kothari, 2009; Best & Kahn, 2003). The principle of replication—that is, the experiment should be repeated more than once; the principle of randomization—that is, we should design or plan the experiment in such a way that the variations caused by extraneous factors can be controlled and the principle of local control—that is, the extraneous factor, the known source of variability, is made to vary deliberately over as wide a range as necessary and this needs to be done in such a way that the variability it causes can be measured and hence eliminated from the experimental error, are the three main principles of an experimental research design. Randomization in experimental research design as mentioned by Kumar (1999) means that any element of the study population has an equal and independent chance of selection at first and being a part of an experimental or control group also. This can be shown in the following diagram:

Figure 1: Randomization in experimental research

It is regarded as the most scientific design because it can establish unambiguous cause-effect relationship. Describing the experimental design, Dornyei (2007) writes:

First, take a group of learners and do something special with/to them, while measuring their progress. Then compare their result with data obtained from another group that is similar in every respect to the first group except for the fact that it did not receive the special treatment. If there is any discrepancy in the result of the two groups, these can be attributed to the only difference between them, the treatment variable. (p.116)

Experimental method is the most sophisticated and powerful method for discovering and developing an organized body of knowledge. Experimenters manipulate certain treatments and observe how the behavior or condition of the subject is changed. So it must be controlled and carefully carried on to remove or control other factors that could influence the outcome. But this control is not very much strict in social science like it is in the natural science or laboratory research. Koul (2000, p. 475) is of the opinion that:

Experimental research is used to determine and evaluate the adequacy and effectiveness of the educational and institutional objectives through the measurements of their outcomes. After evaluating the efficacy of objectives the suggestions are made for the formation, execution and modification of educational programs and classroom practices. The classroom teacher uses experimentation to evaluate the effectiveness of certain learning experiences, planned and organized, to achieve some desired objectives. Effectiveness of teaching methods and innovations in the evaluation techniques is also ascertained through experimental research.

The researcher deliberately controls and manipulates the condition to find out the result, of the manipulated variable to the resulting variable. To clarify it, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2010, p. 272) claim that an experiment involves introducing a change in the value of independent variable and observing the effect of the change on dependent variable. In this sense the independent variable is the input variable and the dependent variable is the outcome variable. Generally, one or more independent variables are manipulated to determine their effect on the dependent variable. Experimental research design is used mostly when the cause precedes the effect, the casual relationship is consistent and the magnitude of the correlation is great. To quote Hatch and Farhady (1982, p. 18):

If you wish to be able to generalize from the result of your classroom experiment to other classrooms, from your students to other students, you will need to choose a design that allows you to share your findings as being relevant to other teachers and other classrooms.

The important point to be assumed is that the generalization may appear wrong if the study population is not randomized and controlled considerably. Kumar (1999, p. 89) says, "for an experiment in a 'natural' environment, the study population is exposed to an intervention in its own environment".

Experimental and control groups

An experiment usually involves comparison between the two or more groups of the result of a treatment with no treatment or a different treatment. A simpler experimental design consists of an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group is exposed to a treatment or the independent variable. In other words, the group that is given the independent variable treatment is called experimental group. On the contrary, control group does not receive any experimental treatment. This group is not exposed to any independent variable for comparison purposes. To quote Hatch and Farhady (1982, p. 18), "a control group refers a group of Ss whose selection and experiences are exactly the same as the experimental group except that they do not receive the experimental treatment". Control group in an experimental research helps to maintain the internal validity of research. The more common control group that receives nothing additional in experimental research in the experiment is distinguished from a placebo control group which receives a placebo.

In educational research, there can be more than one experimental or control groups. Different independent variables can be introduced to different experimental groups in a research. For example, three different methods of teaching

vocabulary can be compared to see which one is better in a particular context. In such cases, the researcher should make sure that all other variables like intelligence, prior knowledge, time of the day, the instructor, length of the instruction, classroom situation, etc. are equated. Simply, in experimental research experimental and control groups are determined by random selection of the participants from the randomly selected sample of the whole study population. This can be shown in the following diagram clearly:

Figure 2: The experimental and control groups in an experimental research

The group that is exposed to the intervention *X* before the post-test is the experimental and the next group post-tested in the business as usual is the control group in Figure 2.

Research variable

Research variables are the factors involved or used in the research activity directly or indirectly. To simplify it, a variable refers to almost anything under the sun. A variable is contrasted with the constant, the other stuff in the world for the researchers. According to Hatch and Farhady (1982, p. 12), "a variable can be defined as an attribute of a person or of an object which 'varies' from person to person or from object to object". Almost any concept, or thing or event, that interests the researcher in a research and that varies or be made to vary is called a variable. For example, height, sex, nationality, mother tongue, person's handedness, etc. are variables assigned to people; weight, shape, size, colour, cost etc. are variables assigned to object and phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic, pragmatic elements are the variables assigned to languages. Within one very broad variable, there can be many other variables.

Researchers mainly pay attention to variables that may influence the result. Variable of specific experimental interest are sometimes referred to as factors.

A variable is an image, perception or concept that can be measured and can be assigned different values (Kumar, 1999, p. 47). Variables are different from the concepts –which are the different mental images or perceptions to different individuals. Variables are measurable with varying degrees of accuracy but concepts are the subjective impressions of individual. To quote Kerlinger (2002, p. 29), "a variable is a symbol to which numbers or values are assigned. For instance X is a variable: it is a symbol to which we assign numerical values". Different types of research variables come into play in an experimental research. Kumar (1999, pp. 51-58) classifies research variables from three different viewpoints, viz. from the viewpoint of causation, from the viewpoint of the study design and from the viewpoint of the unit of measurement. They are briefly mentioned below:

From the viewpoint of causation: This classification of variables is based on cause and effect relationship. There are four types of variables of this kind. They are: a. *Independent variable* – the variable supposed to be responsible for bringing about changes in a phenomenon or situation. It is also called the change, experimental, casual, manipulated, treatment, free or grouping variable. It is the variable which is selected, manipulated, and measured by the researcher. This is the antecedent to the dependent variable in experimental design; b. *Dependent variable* – the variable that undergoes change. This is the outcome variable. The dependent variables are the conditions that appear, disappear, or change as a result of the experimental manipulation in experimental research. Dependent variable is observed and measured to determine the effect of the independent variable; c. *Extraneous variable* – the unmeasured variable that may increase or decrease the magnitude of the relationship between cause and effect. It is affect

variable that affects the relationship between the independent and dependent variable. There are two types of extraneous variables called participant variables – related to individual characteristics of each participant and situation variables–related to things in the environment that may impact on how each participant responds; and d. *Intervening variable*–that links the independent and dependent variable. It is the connecting and linking variable. The independent variables will have assumed effect on the dependent variable only in the presence of an intervening variable. Both extraneous and intervening variables are the types of confounding variables–those aspects of the study which the researcher fails to control or eliminate but that might influence the outcome measures. Confounding variables, thus, are the third variables or the mediator variables. The variables from the viewpoint of causation can be presented in the following diagram:

Figure 3: Variables in cause and effect relationship
From the viewpoint of study design: On the basis of the designs of study variables can be classified into two types, viz. a. *Active variables* - that are changed, manipulated, controlled in the study and b. *Attribute variables* - those that cannot be changed, altered, modified or controlled. They reflect the characteristics of the study population. They are constant variables. Attributes are the sub values of

a variable. Manipulated variables are active variables and measured variables are attribute variables.

From the viewpoint of unit of measurement: On the basis of unit of measurement, variables can at first be classified into whether the measurement is categorical or continuous and qualitative or quantitative in nature. *Categorical variables* can further be classified as *constant* – only one category, *dichotomous* – only two category and *polytomous* – more than two categories. *Continuous variables* have continuity in their measurement, like age (in years), income, weight, class, etc. *Qualitative variables* are similar to categorical variables but we can also develop the continuous variables in qualitative measurement (e. g., age → child/ adult/ old, temperature → hot/cold/ wet, etc.). *Quantitative variables* are similar to continuous variables. We use numbers to measure both the quantitative and continuous variables.

Besides these, there are some other variables commonly discussed in experimental research. They are listed below:

Moderator variable is a special type of independent variable selected to measure whether it modifies the relationship between dependent and independent variables. It is the factor which is measured, manipulated, or selected by the experimenter to discover whether it modifies the relationship of the independent variable to an observed phenomenon. The independent variable's relationship with the dependent variable may change under different conditions. In a study of two methods of teaching reading, one of the methods of teaching reading may work better with boys than girls. Method of teaching reading is the independent variable and reading achievement is the dependent variable. Gender is the moderator variable.

Control variable is the variable held constant in order to neutralize the potential effect it might have on behavior. For example, in the above example, we might only select the boys or girls to control the gender factor. We must notice that the generalizability of our research is limited by using control variables.

Descriptive variables are those which will be reported on, without relating them to anything in particular.

Categorical variables result from a selection from categories, such as 'agree' and 'disagree'. Nominal and ordinal variables are categorical.

Numeric variables give a number, such as age.

Discrete variables are numeric variables that come from a limited set of numbers. They may result from, answering questions such as 'how many', 'how often', etc.

Participant variables are directly involved in the study. They are deliberately and knowingly used by the researchers.

All these variables are directly or indirectly involved in the experimental design. In other words, the whole experimental design is a systematic game played under certain scientific rules among variables (players in the research work, the researcher being the coach). So, we can claim that experimental design is the play of research variables.

Variables can also be classified according to the type of scale on which they are measured. This is the classification according to the type of information which different classifications or measurements provide. A *nominal variable* permits statements to be made only about equality or difference. Therefore, we may say that one individual is the 'same as' or 'different from' another individual. For example, colour of hair, religion, country of birth. An *ordinal variable* permits statements about the rank ordering of the members of a group. Therefore, we may make statements about some characteristics of an individual being 'greater than' or 'less than' other members of a group. For example, physical beauty, richness, happiness. An *interval variable* permits statements about the rank ordering of individuals. It also permits statements to be made about the 'size of the intervals' along the scale which is used to measure the individuals and to compare distances at points along the scale. It is important to note that interval variables do not have true zero points. The numbering of the years in describing dates is an interval scale because the distance between points on the scale is comparable

at any point, but the choice of a zero point is a socio-cultural decision. A *ratio scale* permits all the statements which can be made for the other three types of variables. In addition, a ratio variable has an absolute zero point. This means that a value for this type of variable may be spoken of as 'double' or 'one third of' another value, e.g., height, weight, etc.

This classification is popularly known as measurement scales or variable scales, namely: nominal or classificatory scale, ordinal or ranking scale, interval scale and ratio scale. It is not legitimate to apply simple arithmetic operations to nominal or ordinal variables. Addition and subtraction are possible with interval variables. Where ratio variables are used it is permissible to multiply and divide as well as to add and subtract.

The research process

Any research consists of a series of closely related steps carried out in an order. Such sequenced order of research is called the research process. One should remember that the various steps involved in a research process are not mutually exclusive, nor are they separate and distinct. Kumar (1999) has developed an eight-step model of research process. They are: step 1: formulating research problem, step 2: conceptualizing a research design, step 3: constructing an instrument for data collection, step 4: selecting a sample, step 5: writing a research proposal, step 6: collecting data, step 7: processing data and step 8: writing a research report. The model is generic in nature and can be applied to a number of disciplines in the social sciences. This is presented here:

Figure 4: The research process

Source: Kumar (1999, P. 17)

The model described above provides the comprehensive picture of the research process. Within one step there are many different choices the researcher can select. The researchers are suggested to select the most appropriate activities/ treatments/ procedures for the study. According to Kumar the research process is the collection of all the potential processes to be selected and used appropriately:

It is like a buffet party with eight tables, each with different dishes, but the dishes are made out of similar ingredients. You go to all eight tables and select the dish that you like most from the table. The main difference between the model and the example given is that in the model you select most appropriate for your study and not what you like the most, as in a buffet. (ibid., p. 21)

To use this research process in experimental research design, researchers must concentrate themselves from the second step onwards to differentiate it from other research designs.

Different experimental designs

There are different types of experimental designs. The process and nature of group division or adoption and data collection and analysis depends upon the type of experimental design that the researchers select. The overall experimental designs can be classified as laboratory experiments and field experiments. The terms are very much similar to the terms true experiments and quasi-experiments. Quasi-experiment also includes the pre-experiments in a general sense. In this article, I classify (based on Best and Kahn (2003), Cohen et al. (2010), Hatch and Farhady (1982), Kothari (2009), Koul (2000), Kumar (1999), and Nunan (1993)) the experimental designs into pre-experimental design (three designs), true experimental designs (ten designs), and quasi-experimental designs (four designs). These experimental designs are briefly described below:

The symbol *X* refers to the experimental treatment, *O* refers to the test or observation, *R* refers to random

assignment of groups, *M* refers to the matched groups, *P* refers to placebo treatment, *EV* refers to the experimental variable and *CV* refers to the control variable in the discussion of experimental designs, in this article.

Pre-experimental designs

Per-experimental designs are the least adequate experimental designs because they provide little or no account of extraneous or situation variables which may have influenced the result. Internal validity of such research design is often questioned. But they are still being used in the study of educational problems because they are easy and they provide preliminary information about the study area. There are three most commonly used pre-experimental designs.

Design 1: The one-shot (post-test only) case study design

In this design, the only experimental group is given some experimental treatment for a given period of time. After that the group receives the post-test. Then, the result of the treatment is carefully compared with the base-line (general expectation of what would happen without the treatment or information available in existing records) observations. The schematics representation of this design is:

$$\text{Experimental} \quad X \quad O$$

Treatment effect = *O* - baseline

But the results of such design are not generalizable and valid. There are many extraneous variables that could have helped /obstructed a lot to produce the result discovered.

Design 2: The one group pretest post-test design

In this design, pretest is also administered before the treatment is exposed to the only experimental group. So there are two tests (*O*₁ and *O*₂) before and after the treatment (*X*) is introduced. Symbolically it can be presented as:

$$\text{Experimental} \quad O_1 \quad X \quad O_2$$

Treatment effect = *O*₂ - *O*₁

Any change in the dependent variable in the pretest and post-test observations of the group is

attributed to the intervention or treatment or the experimental manipulation. This design also may suffer from the problems of Design 1 because it also lacks a control group. We still cannot make justified claims about the effect of the treatment.

Design 3: The two static/ intact/ non-equivalent group post-test only design

To overcome the limitations of Design 1 and Design 2, this design utilizes a control group also, which permits the comparison with the one exposed to the experimental treatment, i.e. experimental group. But the group members are not assigned randomly in this design. Most classroom researchers use this design. We can toss a coin to determine which of the two groups gets the experimental treatment. Schematic representation of this design is;

<i>Experimental</i>	<i>X</i>	O_1
<i>Control</i>		O_2

Treatment effect = $O_1 - O_2$

Although this appears similar to a true experimental design, the lack of pretest, of matched groups, of random allocation and of controls, result it a flawed methodology (Cohen et al. 2010, p. 283).

True experimental designs

A true experimental design consists of an intervention study, which contains at least two groups: the treatment or experimental group, which receives the special treatment and the control group: which provides a baseline for comparison (Dorinye, 2007, p. 116). This is the most appropriate way to resolve a question about language learning or teaching (Brown & Rodgers, 2002, p. 195). The subjects in the experimental research are assigned to either the control or experimental group randomly to be such that both the groups of subjects before the experiment are really the same or equal (Nunan, 1993, p. 27). This strengthens the internal and external validity of the experiment. It is difficult to arrange a true experimental design in school classroom research because the equivalence of the experimental and control groups should be assured by random assignment of subjects to each groups.

But this is the strongly suggested design wherever possible (Best & Kahn, 2003, p. 174). The key features of true experimental design according to Cohen et al. (2010, p. 275) are one or more control groups, one or more experimental groups, random allocation to control and experimental groups, pretest of the groups to ensure parity, post-test of the groups to see the effect on the dependent variable, one or more intervention to the experimental groups, isolation, control and manipulation of independent variables, and non-contamination between the control and experimental groups. The main true experimental designs are shortly discussed below:

Design 4: The randomized two groups post-test only design

This design is a simplest and powerful experimental design that minimizes the threats to experimental validity. The participants are randomly assigned to two different groups at first and the decision as to which groups will be the experimental group is also decided randomly, e.g., by a flip of a coin, in this design. The experimental group alone receives the intervention and finally both groups are given only a post-test. The design is:

<i>Experimental</i>	R_1	<i>X</i>	O_1
<i>Control</i>	R_2		O_2

Treatment effect = $O_1 - O_2$

It is believed that random selection of the subjects to two different group from the same population controls all possible extraneous variables, and keeps both the groups in the equidistance in research, before the intervention is introduced.

Design 5: The randomized two groups matched pairs post-test only design

The participants are assigned to control and experimental groups randomly on an individual-by-individual basis in this design. It uses a technique of matching to the members of control and experimental groups on the several independent variables important for the study, such as age, gender, ability, mother tongue, geographical region, class position, score in exams,

ethnicity, etc. instead of random assignment of the subjects to each group in Design 4. All other processes are the same. Matching should be done on an early identifiable characteristic otherwise it increases difficulty. One way of addressing this is to place all the subjects in rank order on the basis of the score or measures of the dependent variable, if available. Then, the first two subjects become one matched pair, second two subjects become the next pair and so on until the sample is drawn. Individual members of each pairs are assigned to two different groups and the control or experimental group is determined randomly, (e.g., by tossing a coin). Schematic representation of this design is:

<i>Experimental</i>	<i>RM₁</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>O₁</i>
<i>Control</i>	<i>RM₂</i>		<i>O₂</i>

Treatment effect = $O_1 - O_2$

But this design is believed to be a far inferior means of ruling out alternative casual explanations than randomization.

Design 6: The randomized two groups pretest post-test design

This design is the same as Design 4 except a pretest is administered before the treatment to both the experimental and control group. This is also called the randomized control-group pretest post-test design. This can be presented symbolically as:

<i>Experimental</i>	<i>R₁O₁</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>O₂</i>
<i>Control</i>	<i>R₂O₃</i>		<i>O₄</i>

Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$

It should be considered well in this design that the time between the pretest and post-test should be considerable - at least two weeks as a general rule of thumb.

Design 7: The randomized two experimental group post-test only design

The participants are randomly assigned to two different experimental groups and two different experimental treatments are introduced; one each to both the experimental groups, in this design. Only post-test is administered to both groups. Schematic representation of this design is:

<i>Experimental₁</i>	<i>R₁</i>	<i>X₁</i>	<i>O₁</i>
<i>Experimental₂</i>	<i>R₂</i>	<i>X₂</i>	<i>O₂</i>

Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1)$ or $(O_1 - O_2)$

This is a comparative experimental design where the sample population is divided into same number of groups as per the number of treatment to be tested. So, the group can be divided into three or four according to the number of treatment to be introduced. Then, the score of the post-test of each group is compared.

Design 8: The randomized two experimental groups pretest post-test design

This is the same design as the Design 7 except a pretest is administered to both groups before the intervention is introduced. The design is symbolized as:

<i>Experimental₁</i>	<i>R₁O₁</i>	<i>X₁</i>	<i>O₂</i>
<i>Experimental₂</i>	<i>R₂O₃</i>	<i>X₂</i>	<i>O₄</i>

Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$ or $(O_4 - O_3) - (O_2 - O_1)$

One more control group can also be added with the two (or more) experimental groups to modify this design. This, thus, might yield the design:

<i>Experiment₁</i>	<i>R₁O₁</i>	<i>X₁</i>	<i>O₂</i>
<i>Experimental₂</i>	<i>R₂O₃</i>	<i>X₂</i>	<i>O₄</i>
<i>Control</i>	<i>R₃O₅</i>		<i>O₆</i>

Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_6 - O_5)$ or $(O_4 - O_3) - (O_6 - O_5)$ or $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$ or $(O_4 - O_3) - (O_2 - O_1)$

To quote Cohen et al. (2010, p. 279) "this can be extended to the post-test control and experimental group design and the post-test two experimental groups design, and the pretest-post-test two treatment design".

Design 9: The randomized Solomon three groups design

This design is suggested by R. L. Solomon. It uses three groups with random assignment of subjects to groups. It consists of two control group instead of one, in Design 6. In the Solomon variant the second control group is exposed to the

experimental treatment but is not pretested. Thus, the design is:

<i>Experimental</i>	R_1O_1	X	O_2
<i>Control₁</i>	R_2O_3		O_4
<i>Control₂</i>	R_3	X	O_5

Treatment effect = $(O_3 - O_4)$ or $(O_5 - O_2)$ or $(O_2 - O_4) - (O_4 - O_3)$

This experimental design helps to overcome the reactive or interactive effect of pretest and the experimental treatment by the addition of second control group. It can control most of the extraneous variables.

Design 10: The randomized Solomon four groups design

This design consists of randomly selected four groups with one more control group than in Design 9. Among the four groups the experimental group and one of the control groups receive a pretest. The other two control groups are not pretested and only one of them receives the experimental treatment. All the four groups receive post-test. This can be modeled thus as:

<i>Experimental</i>	R_1O_1	X	O_2
<i>Control₁</i>	R_2O_3		O_4
<i>Control₂</i>	R_3	X	O_5
<i>Control₃</i>	R_4		O_6

Treatment effect = $(O_5 - O_6)$ or $(O_5 - O_4)$ or $(O_5 - O_2)$ or $(O_2 - O_4) - (O_4 - O_3)$

This design also provides control over any possible contemporary effects that may occur between pretesting and post-testing. Thus it permits the evaluation of the effects of testing, history and maturation.

Design 11: The randomized five group parametric design

In this design, participants are randomly assigned to groups whose parameters are fixed in terms of the independent variable that each receives (Cohen et al., 2010, p. 281). For example if an experiment is conducted to improve the reading abilities of poor, average, good and outstanding readers, four experimental groups are set up to receive the

experimental treatment, viz. poor readers group, average readers group, good readers group and outstanding readers group along with the (fifth) control group receiving no treatment (ibid.). This can be presented symbolically as:

<i>Experimental₁</i>	R_1	X	O_1
<i>Experimental₂</i>	R_2	X	O_2
<i>Experimental₃</i>	R_3	X	O_3
<i>Experimental₄</i>	R_4	X	O_4
<i>Control</i>	R_5		O_5

Treatment effect = $(O_1 - O_5)$ or $(O_2 - O_5)$ or $(O_3 - O_5)$ or $(O_4 - O_5)$

Parametric designs are useful if an independent variable is considered to have different levels or a range of values which may have a bearing on the outcome or if the researcher wishes to discover whether different levels of an independent variable have an effect on the outcome (ibid.).

Design 12: The randomized factorial designs

Factorial designs are used in experiments where the effects of varying more than one factor are to be determined. They are not the designs in themselves. They are simply the addition of more variables to other designs. There will be more than one independent variable (i.e. moderate variable) considered and the variables may have one or more levels (Hatch & Farhatdy, 1982, p. 28). By using factorial designs researchers can determine the treatment with two factors. For example, if the treatment interacts significantly with gender or age. In this design participants are randomly assigned to groups that cover all the possible combinations of levels of each independent variable.

Factional design is different from other common true experimental design in that other design are confined to single variable design which require that a experimenter manipulates one independent variable to produce effect on the dependent variable. But the independent variable alone may not produce the same effect as it might in interaction with another independent variable. Thus, the findings from a one variable design are questioned. For instance, the

effectiveness of new teaching technique depends upon a number of variables like the intelligence level of students, their background knowledge, and so no. In such an experiment, the classical one variable design would not reveal any information about the interactive effect of the method and intelligence level of the students and any other variable (Koul, 2000, p. 496). To overcome this problem R.A. Fisher developed factorial design that enables the experimenter to evaluate or manipulate two or more variables simultaneously in order to study effects of number of independent variables singly as well as the effects due to interactions with one another.

Factorial design can be carried out as a separate experimental research design or even as a quasi-experimental design. It is described as a true experimental design in this article. Factorial designs vary according to the degree of complexity depending upon the nature and purpose of experiment. The most common types of factorial designs are discussed here:

Design 12 a: Simple factorial design

In this design, the effects of varying two factors are considered on the dependent variable. There are two independent variables and each of the independent variables has two values. The first independent variable which is manipulated and has two value is called the experimental variable (EV) and the independent variable which is divided into levels may be called the control variable (CV). This design is also called the 'two-factor-factorial design.' Simple factorial design can either be a 2 × 2 simple factorial design or 3 × 4 or 5 × 3 or the like type of simple factorial design. These are illustrated below:

2 × 2 simple factorial design

In this design, extraneous variable to be controlled is the control variable and the independent variable that is manipulated is experimental variable. There are two treatments each in the experimental and control variables which yield the sample divided into four cells. Each of the four combinations provides one treatment or experimental condition.

Subjects are assigned to each treatment randomly. The means for each cell is obtained along with the means for different rows and columns. Mean of individual cells represent the mean scores for the independent variable, column means shows the main effect for the treatment without taking into account any differential effect that is due to the level of the control variable, and row means shows the main effects for levels of control without regard to treatment. We get the main effects of treatments and the main effects of levels from this design. We can also examine the interaction between treatments and levels which shows whether the treatment and levels are independent of each other or not (Kothari, 2009, pp. 47-48). It is illustrated in this figure:

Figure 5: 2 × 2 simple factorial design

The 2 × 2 design may also be of the type having two experimental variables or two control variables unlike the Figure 5.

4 × 3 simple factorial design

The 4 × 3 simple factorial design will usually include four treatments of the experimental variables and three levels of the control variable (ibid., p. 49). Graphically it can be presented as:

Figure 6: 4 × 3 simple factorial design

This shows that a 2 × 2 simple factorial design can be generalized to any number of treatments and levels. Accordingly we can name it such and such (--- × ---) design (ibid., p. 49).

Design 12b: Complex factorial design

This design is used to experiment more than two factors at a time. It has three or more independent variables occurring simultaneously in a study. In the case of three factors with one experimental variable having two treatments and two control variables, every one of which has two levels, the design used will be termed $2 \times 2 \times 2$ complex factorial design which contains a total of eight cells (ibid., p. 50). We can show it in this figure:

Figure 7: $2 \times 2 \times 2$ complex factorial design

The main effects of the three variables (one experimental and two controls) can be determined in this design. The interaction between each possible pair of variables and interaction between variables taken in triplets ($EC \times CV_1$, $EV \times CV_2$ and $CV_1 \times CV_2$) can also be determined. There can be the next order interaction between all three variables symbolically $EC \times CV_1 \times CV_2$. The researcher must ignore the control variables 2 (CV_2) to obtain the interaction of $EV \times CV_1$ and the design is simplified to 2×2 design from $2 \times 2 \times 2$ design by combining the data of the relevant cells. The complex factorial design can further be clarified from the following pictorial presentation (ibid.):

Figure 8: $2 \times 2 \times 2$ complex factorial design

The dotted line cell in the diagram is cell 1 and is for treatment A, level I for the control variable 1, and level I of control variable 2. All other cells are also numbered in the figure except cell 6 that is hidden by cell 2. The analysis of the first order interaction ($EV \times CV_1$, $EV \times CV_2$ or $CV_1 \times CV_2$) is a simple factorial analysis because only two variables are considered at a time and the remaining one is ignored. The analysis of the second order interaction ($EV \times CV_1 \times CV_2$) uses all three independent variables in the cases of $2 \times 2 \times 2$ design. This analysis is called the complex factorial design. But it need not necessarily be of the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ type only. It can be generalized to any combination of experimental and control independent variables. If the greater numbers of independent variables are included in a complex factorial design, the higher order of interaction analysis is possible. To quote Kothari (2009, p. 51), "but the task goes on becoming more and more complicated with the inclusion of more and more independent variables in our design".

Design 13: The randomized repeated measures design

In this design the participants are randomly assigned into different experimental groups as per the number of intervention to be introduced. This design may or may not include a control condition. This is a variant of Design 5, but offers considerable control potential because it is the same group receiving different intervention. The three interventions to six different experimental groups randomly selected, for example, goes in this order:

Group 1 receives intervention 1, 2 and 3 respectively; group 2 receives intervention 2, 3 and 1 respectively; group 3 receives intervention 3, 1 and 2 respectively; group 4 receives intervention 1, 3 and 2 respectively; group 5 receives intervention 2, 1 and 3 respectively and group 6 receives intervention 3, 2 and 1 respectively. Symbolically this can be shown as:

*Experimental*₁ R₁O₁ X O₂ X₁ O₃ X₂ O₄
*Experimental*₂ R₂O₅ X₁ O₆ X₂ O₇ X₁ O₈
*Experimental*₃ R₃O₉ X₂ O₁₀ X₁ O₁₁ X₁ O₁₂
*Experimental*₄ R₄O₁₃ X₁ O₁₄ X₂ O₁₅ X₁ O₁₆
*Experimental*₅ R₅O₁₇ X₁ O₁₈ X₁ O₁₉ X₂ O₂₀
*Experimental*₆ R₆O₂₁ X₂ O₂₂ X₁ O₂₃ X₁ O₂₄

Treatment effect = (O₂₄ - O₂₁), (O₂₀ - O₁₇), (O₁₆ - O₁₃), (O₁₂ - O₉), (O₈ - O₅) or (O₄ - O₁) etc.

To quote Cohen et al. (2010, p. 282):

Repeated measures design are useful if it is considered that order effect are either unimportant or unlikely, or if the researcher cannot be certain that individual differences will not obscure treatment effects, as it enables these individual differences to be controlled.

To overcome the order effects in repeated measures design we can randomize both the intervention and the participants to different groups.

Quasi-experimental design

Quasi means 'as if', and thus, quasi-experiment is not a true experiment but only a variant on it. While carrying out an experiment is difficult by different causes, we then move to quasi-experiment. It is an alternative to the laboratory experiment, and it is also called the field experiment (Cohen et al. 2010, p. 275). It is not always possible to rearrange the numbers into different groups at will, and researcher is compelled to carry out the experiment with intact groups of subjects, that is, subjects who have been grouped for reason other than the carrying out an experiment. This experiment is quasi-experiment rather than true experimental (Nunan 1993, p. 27). Quasi-experiments do not use random assignment and thus, non-equivalent groups are compared in the study (Dornyei, 2007, p. 117). Much of research follows the quasi-experimental designs because of the rigidity of true experimental design. The concept of experimental design is an idealized abstraction only. Pre-experimental researcher designs are also the quasi-experimental designs.

"Quasi-experimental designs are practical compromises between true experimentation and the nature of human language behavior which we wish to investigate", for Hatch and Farhady (1982, p. 24). It provides considerable and required flexibility under the existing condition. Avoiding the situations where by members self-select themselves to be in the treatment group and minimizing pre-test differences between the treatment and the control groups as much as possible, are the two specific ways for improving this design (Dornyei, 2007, p. 117). The followings are the most common quasi-experimental designs:

Design 14: The non-randomized two groups pretest post-test design

In this design the experimental and control groups are the naturally assembled intact or static groups. This is the most commonly used quasi-experimental design in educational research. Both the groups are given the pretest and post-test. The design can be represented as:

<i>Experimental</i>	O ₁	X	O ₂
<i>Control</i>	O ₃		O ₄

Treatment effect = (O₂ - O₁) - (O₄ - O₃)

This design is an addition of a control group to Design 2 of pre-experimental design. Once the two groups are obtained it is advisable to use a random procedure to determine which groups is to be assigned to experimental treatment and which one to the controlled condition in this design also.

Design 15: The time series designs

Sometimes time series designs are also identified as different experimental designs. But we describe them as quasi-experimental here. In these designs subjects are administered several pretests and post-tests. There are four types of time series designs. They are:

Design 15a: The one-group time series design

This design is similar to Design 2, but a series of tests-measurements are taken before and after the group is exposed to the experimental treatment. Symbolically:

Experimental $O_1 O_2 O_3 O_4 X O_5 O_6 O_7 O_8$

Then the treatment effect is measured between the test intervals and the score among the tests is compared. Following graph can be used to explain the treatment effect:

Figure 9: Treatment effects of one-group time series design

If a line similar to line 1 is obtained, it shows that the treatment has no effect, line 2 shows the negative effect and line three shows that the treatment is effective.

Design 15b: The equivalent time sample design

In this design, the treatment is introduced and reintroduced between every other pretest and post-test. In other words, the treatment is introduced after the first pretest and is followed by a post-test. Then, after the second pretest an alternative treatment (non-treatment) is introduced and that is also followed by a post-test. This procedure is followed for two or three times. This can be shown symbolically as:

Experimental $O_1 X O_2 \rightarrow O_3 O_4 \rightarrow O_5 X O_6 \rightarrow O_7 O_8$
 Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$ or $(O_6 - O_5) - (O_8 - O_7)$

The number of observation and intervention may vary. This helps the researcher to discover the maturation effect of test (and retest) and the effect of treatment in the experiment.

Design 15c: The equivalent materials single group pretest post-test design

In this design the same group is used as a control group once and as an experimental group the next time. The order of exposure to experimental and

control group can be reversed – first experimental and then control. Symbolically:

Experimental $O_1 X_0 O_2 O_3 X O_4$
 Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$

The selected treatment (X_0 and X) must be equally interested and difficult to the subjects (students). But it is very difficult to select equated materials to be learned. Some of its limitations can be minimized partially by a series of replications in which the order of exposure to experimental and controlled treatments is reversed. This process is known as rotation, which can be illustrated in the following four cycle experiment:

$$\frac{I}{\text{Experimental } O_1 X O_2 O_3 X_0 O_4} \quad \frac{II}{O_5 X_0 O_6 O_7 X O_8} \quad \frac{III}{O_9 O_{10} O_{11} O_{12}} \quad \frac{IV}{O_{13} O_{14} O_{15} O_{16}}$$

If the experimental treatment yielded significantly greater gains regardless of the order of exposure, its effectiveness could be accepted with greater confidence.

Design 15d: The control group time series design

In this design, a control group is added to Design 15a. The control group is also an intact class group. This group is also introduced with a series of pretest and post-test but is not exposed to the experimental treatment. The design is:

Experimental $O_1 O_2 O_3 O_4 X O_5 O_6 O_7 O_8$
 Control $O_9 O_{10} O_{11} O_{12} O_{13} O_{14} O_{15} O_{16}$
 Treatment effect = $(O_8 - O_4) - (O_{16} - O_{12})$ or $(O_8 - O_1) - (O_{16} - O_9)$, etc.

The inclusion of control group is useful for necessary comparison in this design.

Design 16: The counterbalanced design

In this design, different experimental groups selected from the intact classes (non-randomly) are introduced equal number of treatments by rotating the groups at periodic intervals during the experiment. Each group of the subjects is expose to such experimental treatment (X) at different times (the replication of treatment) during the experiment. This design is similar to Design 13. But the groups

here are not selected randomly. Symbolically it can be presented as:

*Experimental*₁ O_1 X O_2 X_1 O_3 X_2 O_4 X_3 O_5
*Experimental*₂ O_6 X_1 O_7 X_2 O_8 X_3 O_9 X O_{10}
*Experimental*₃ O_{11} X_2 O_{12} X_3 O_{13} X O_{14} X_1 O_{15}
*Experimental*₄ O_{16} X_3 O_{17} X O_{18} X_1 O_{19} X_2 O_{20}
 Treatment effect = $(O_5 - O_1)$, $(O_{10} - O_6)$, $(O_{15} - O_{11})$, $(O_{20} - O_{16})$, etc.

Each group receives all treatments, and each treatment is first, second, third and fourth in the order received by one of the groups. Each group is exposed to each treatment once. This design has excellent internal validity because history, maturation, regression, selection and mortality are all, generally, well controlled. This design is also known as rotation group design, crossover design or switchover design.

Design 17: The non-randomized (intact) two group placebo design

In this design the researcher selects two naturally occurring intact groups and randomly assigns them as experimental and placebo control groups. The experimental group receives the experimental treatment and the placebo group receives the placebo treatment. The placebos are the substitute to the experimental treatments indistinguishable to both the experimental groups and the control (placebo here) groups. Especially it is used in medical research. Placebo control group is a group receiving a placebo to distinguish it from the more common control group that receives nothing additional. Simply speaking, placebo is the fake treatment in research, used to avoid experimental research from treatment receiving and non-receiving group comparison. Symbolically this can be presented as:

Experimental O_1 X O_2
Placebo O_3 P O_4
 Treatment effect = $(O_2 - O_1)$ or $(O_4 - O_3)$ or $(O_2 - O_4)$ or $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$

The placebo designs are of two kinds; viz. blind studies design – when the subjects do not know

whether they are getting real or fake treatment and double-blind studies design – when the researcher also does not know the identity of experimental groups. In a double-blind study neither the researcher nor the subjects know who is receiving real and who is receiving fake treatment.

Validity in experimental research

In all the experimental designs discussed above, the main purpose is to impose control over conditions that would otherwise cloud the real effect of the experimental variables upon the dependent variables. Cohen et al. (2010) suggest that those clouding conditions threaten to jeopardize the validity of experiments. There are two general types of validity in experimental research viz. internal validity and external validity. If the variables identified have the systematic and genuine effect on the dependent variable and the observed effect is not affected by the extraneous or situational variables then the experiment has the internal validity and if the relationship measured, isolated and classified can be generalized outside the experimental setting, it possesses external validity. In other words, external validity is the extent to which the variable relationship can be generalized to other settings, other treatment variables, other measurement variables and other population (Best & Kahn, 2003, p. 116). Ensuring internal and external validity is very important in experimental research.

There are a number of factors that jeopardize the validity of experimental research. Such factors affecting the internal and external validity of experimental research as cited in Cohen et al. (2010), Best and Kahn (2003) and Koul (2000) according to Campbell and Stanley (1963) and others are discussed below with some suggestions to overcome them:

Factors jeopardizing internal validity

The main factors that jeopardize the internal validity of an experimental research - also called the threads to internal validity, are given below with short description:

History: It is the effect of other factors except the experimental treatment that may occur between the first and second measurements (pretest and post-test). The effects produced by such events can mistakenly be attributed to differences in treatment. The researcher should try to control such specific events.

Maturation: The subjects may perform differently in many ways over time, on different occasions as a result of biological or psychological processes like fatigue, age, interest, or motivation but such differences may be confusingly attributed to the effect of treatment variable under study. Such effect can be minimized by randomly assigning subjects to experimental and control group, controlling other extraneous variables and building good rapport with the study population.

Testing: The exposure of the subjects to the pretest at the beginning of experiment can produce effect of practice or experience which may result specific performance in the post-test. Such effect can be controlled by having an equivalent control group, and a well-recognized gap (e.g., of at least two weeks) between pretest and post-test.

Unstable instrumentation: Unreliable tests or other instruments or techniques can also introduce serious errors and threats to the validity of experiment. This can be controlled by piloting the instruments and careful planning.

Statistical regression: It is the tendency of the extreme scores to regress or move towards the common mean in the subsequent measurements. As a result the subjects scoring highest on the pretest are likely to score relatively lower on the post-test and those scoring lowest in the pretest are likely to score relatively higher on the post-test. But such effect may be interpreted as an effect due to the experimental treatment. Random selection or the random selection of matched subjects can control this effect.

Selection bias: Selection bias occurs by the non-randomized selection of experimental and control

group. This mainly happens in the studies where the subjects in experimental groups are chosen on invitation or by volunteer selection of the subjects or intact classes are used as experimental and control groups. This can well be controlled. Randomly selected experimental and control groups can reduce this problem.

Experimental mortality: It is the loss or mortality of the subjects from the comparison groups. For example, the subjects scoring the lowest may drop out from the experimental group after the pretest. This effect can be controlled by shortening the experiment as far as possible or even by maintaining the privacy of the test results until the research finishes.

Experimental bias: This is the subjective evaluation and personal help of the researcher intentionally to affect the groups' reaction. This happens especially in the placebo research if the researcher is administering the treatments himself/herself to the experimental and placebo control group when some clues are provided to the groups that affect subjects' reaction. To control this contamination we can conduct the double blind studies, where someone other than the experimenter administers the treatment and records which subjects are receiving the real treatment and which the fake treatment (placebo).

Selection-maturation interaction: This occurs when there is confusion between the research design effects and variable effects. When two comparison groups have the same score on the pretest, some other factors due to interaction between the variables such as intelligence, motivation, interest, age, etc. rather than experimental variable may cause one of the groups to perform well on the post-test. To control this problem, we should select the subjects randomly rather than on the basis of other extraneous factors.

Instrument reactivity: It is the effect that the instruments of the study compel on the subjects of

the study. Even if the instruments used are good, they may not be considered equally facilitating, encouraging, and friendly by all the subjects. To solve this effect, the researchers should consider the context and general norms, values, trends of the respondents.

Factors jeopardizing external validity

The followings are the main threats to external validity of experimental research. These threats are the factors jeopardizing external validity.

Failure to describe independent variable: If the independent variables are not well defined it is impossible for future replication research. So, the researcher must identify, describe, and define the independent variable of study comprehensively.

Interference of prior treatment: The subjects carry the effect of the previous treatments to the latter ones. This mainly happens when there is no control group, but the same group receives different treatments at different order of time. This problem can be solved by introducing control group randomly selected.

Lack of representativeness of available and target population: If the sample selected or population available is not representative of the population to which the result is generalized it creates problems. To control this issue the researcher should build strong sampling and randomization procedure.

Artificiality of the experimental setting: If the atmosphere created in the research is a sterile and artificial in the name of control, the rigidity of control does not produce generalizable result. For this, researchers should control the extraneous variables only when they are likely to pollute the study completely or partially.

Howthron effect: When the individual subjects notice that they are being observed, they may change their behavior which results their increased or decreased productivity. Their realization of their roles as guinea pig may result different performance

than their natural and usual performance. This Howthron effect of the subjects is also regarded as the influence of the experimental treatment. This effect can be reduced by building rapport with the learners and hiding the purpose if it is considered ethical at all.

Inadequate operationalizing of dependent variables: Being concerned much on the independent variable only to create some change on the dependent variable the researcher may not use the dependent variable appropriately. The conclusion reached may reflect the researcher's subjective interpretation. Many other aspects regarding the dependent variables may have been missed. The researcher must consider about it very well.

The extent of the treatment verification: If the researcher uses researcher assistants who are not directly involved in the formulation of research hypothesis, the administration of the research tools etc., this may lead to a potential threat to external validity. The researcher must observe, and administer the treatment and the research tools properly.

Sensitization/reactivity to experimental conditions: The pretest administered to the subjects before the introduction of experimental treatment may change subjects' sensitivity to the experimental treatment clouding the effect of the experimental research. In this sense, this is different from the problem of testing as the threat to internal validity. This can be controlled easily by introducing a control group in the study.

Interaction effects of extraneous factors and experimental treatments: The experimental treatment may have produced the specified result with the considerable interaction with the extraneous variables. But it is mistakenly attributed to the experimental treatment only. This can be controlled by avoiding the extraneous variables carefully when they are likely to affect the result.

Effect of non-randomized selection: If the subjects are selected from the intact groups, the result produced is questioned and it lacks external validity. The researcher should select and group the subjects randomly.

Invalidity or unreliability of instruments: The validity and reliability of the research tools is the main parameter to make the research purposive and confidential. So, the research instruments must be piloted and revised accordingly before the final administration. Invalid research tools result the invalid experimentation.

Ecological validity: The experimental design may lack the ecological validity when behavior observed in a certain context cannot be generalized to another. The researcher must pay increased attention on the extension of the study, experimental arrangement, representativeness of the independent and dependent variables, the reactive effects of the variables and the participants and selection of appropriate and contextual research instruments to achieve ecological validity.

Conclusion

Experimental research designs are also called the interventional research designs because the researcher manipulates a situation and measures the effects of the manipulation. Most often two groups are compared. Intervention or experimental treatment takes place in one of these groups. The main purpose of experimental research is to investigate possible cause and effect relationships by exposing one or more experimental groups to one or more experimental treatment conditions and comparing the results to one or more control groups not receiving the experimental treatment. The researcher eliminates the effect of intervening variables and bias by randomization in experimental research. Different phases and activities in an experimental study can be displayed in the following figure:

Figure 10: Diagram of an experimental study

Source: Wolff and Pant (2008, p. 112)

We can get the reliable knowledge when we use the experimental method. But there are many difficulties in conducting the true experimental studies in social sciences because of its rigidity. It is rarely feasible with human population especially in the field of language teaching and learning. It requires rigorous management of experimental variables and conditions and uses a control group as a baseline against which the experimental treatment receiving group(s) is (are) compared.

The discussion above shows that even though experimental approach is the most powerful, it is also the most restrictive and artificial. The quasi-experimental research designs are also suggested considering the limitations in applying strictly controlled experimental research in social sciences. They assist to approximate the conditions of the experiment in a setting, which does not allow the control and/ or manipulation of all relevant variables. However, manipulation of an independent variable that serves as an intervention is always included in quasi-experimental study also. Thus, experimental design, either it be true experiment or the quasi-experiment, is the systematic and organized play of research variables under considerable restriction or control.

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